

PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

How to use this consent form: We ask you to take your time to read the following Data Consent form. You can only participate in research conducted for PRODIGEES if you give your consent to the use of your data. The results of the research will be published for open access in the PRODIGEES' online repository (Zenodo).

Data Consent Form

Who is responsible for processing your data?

Responsible authority for the processing of your data is:

German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
PRODIGEES
Tulpenfeld 6
53113 Bonn

Contact for questions regarding the processing of your data:

Wulf Reiners
PRODIGEES Co-Coordinator
Tulpenfeld 6
53113 Bonn
wulf.reiners@idos-research.de

AND

Sven Grimm
PRODIGEES Co-Coordinator
Tulpenfeld 6
53113 Bonn
sven.grimm@idos-research.de

The Data Protection Officer responsible is:

German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
GBD GmbH
Hans Bachem
Datenschutzbeauftragter
Tel: 02424 7275

Mobil: 0171 2114166
gbd.bachem@t-online.de

Each institution has assigned respective Data Protection Officers, as follows:

Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI)

Ing. Claudio Roma
Register of Engineers of the Province of Rome, no.18383
Tel.: +39 (0) 63 5510 107
Email: serim.cr@tin.it

Universität Hamburg (UHAM)

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Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)

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Luiss Guido Carli University (LUISS)

Francesco Flego
Head of Data Protection
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Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften - Institut für Technikfolgen-Abschätzung (OEAW-ITA)

Kathrin Bösenkopf
Legal and Compliance Officer
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Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS)

Dr. K. Ravi Srinivas
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Stellenbosch University (SU)

Jerall Toi

Tel.: +27 21 808 4139

Email: jerall@sun.ac.za

For what purpose will your data be processed?

In principle, your personal data will only be processed within the conditions of your membership in PRODIGEES Project, which includes the online repository where the results of the research will be stored for open access. According to Article 6 EU-GDPR, we need your informed consent in order to process and store your personal data. The data is stored in order to facilitate the research projects under the PRODIGEES framework. Your data will only be used for anonymous research purposes unless otherwise explicitly stated by the research team and with your consent.

What personal data is processed?

The following personal data will be collected and used:

Data collected for registration with PRODIGEES:

- Name, city, and country of origin in order to maintain your identity
- Date of birth to ensure that you are of age
- Email address to communicate with you before, during, and after the research, unless otherwise requested

Data collected when using PRODIGEES:

- Information published by you to PRODIGEES
- Social media contributions such as comments, news, likes, ratings, pictures, or announcements, which can be used for the provision of the website
- IP address, information about your device, as well as your browser, URL information, time of request, cookie data, online identifiers, and server logs

We record behavioural and analytical data regarding the use of PRODIGEES web pages. This helps us to improve our platform and allows us measure the performance of the website.

Data that you can provide optionally and voluntarily:

- Telephone number
- Additional profile data (i.e. profile picture, lifestyle information, etc.)

Who is the recipient of your data?

We have selected to host the PRODIGEES online repository on well-known and secure servers. We have taken the greatest care in selecting these service providers and review them periodically to ensure that your privacy is protected.

For how long will your data be stored?

Your personal data will be stored for the length of the PRODIGEES project and up to 5 years afterwards, unless otherwise objected to by withdrawing your consent. You may request for your personal information to be destroyed at any time. The information is held for the case of further analysis, reanalysis and auditing.

What rights do you have?

Regarding your personal data, you have the following rights according to Chapter III GDPR, which you can claim at any time from the contact person mentioned above:

- Article 15 EU-GDPR: You have the right to information and may request a copy of your data processed by us.
- Article 16 EU-GDPR: You have the right to make corrections and make sure that your data is complete.
- Article 17 EU-GDPR: You have the right to delete your personal data (otherwise stated as the "right to be forgotten").
- Article 18 EU-GDPR: You have the right to demand from the person responsible the limitation of the processing of your personal data.
- Article 21 EU-GDPR: You have the right to object at any time to the processing of your relevant data.
- Article 7 EU-GDPR, you have the right to withdraw consent to the processing of your personal data at any time. When you withdraw your consent, the personal data used between your acquiescence to consent and your withdrawal of consent is lawfully used data.

Herewith I agree to the processing of my personal data in the above scope, by the description of the PRODIGEES Data Protection Polity and for the purposes stated therein, by the responsible persons. I have received the information required under the EU General Data Protection Regulations (EU-GDPR). I am content with the conditions as well as the rights granted to me under this agreement.

Date_____

Signature of Research Participant_____

Date_____

Signature of Researcher_____

